
Prepositions, postpositions, and disharmonic word order in Zarma

Waheed Ayisa Jayeola¹

¹*Department of Linguistics and African Languages, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria,*
wajayeola@oauife.edu.ng

*Corresponding author

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Abstract: Zarma, a member of the Songhay language family, is arguably a non-configurational language; it attests Verb Object and Object Verb orders and displays prepositions and postpositions with a greater degree of disharmony. Also, available data show that prepositions and postpositions that are derived diachronically from verbs and location nouns, respectively, a feature commonly associated with subject-verb-object languages, are attested in Zarma. However, the language's internal properties of the derived postpositions and the location nouns vis-à-vis the mixed or disharmonic cross-categorial word order have not received adequate attention. Therefore, this paper adopts the analytical approach of the Linear Correspondence Axiom (LCA) to explain the mixed and disharmonic nature of preposition/postposition phrases in Zarma. The work is qualitative, and the data used were sourced primarily from native speakers, while other relevant data were collected from published works, such as linguistic articles and written texts. This paper reveals that a number of the postpositions in Zarma are derived from nouns through grammaticalization that is mediated by genitive constructions, but it is not clear whether the few prepositions actually evolve from verbs. The derived postpositions and location nouns share some properties and also differ to certain limits. Contrary to claims in extant studies, this paper shows that prepositions and postpositions are not distinguishable on the basis of case-assigning functions. Thus, Zarma prepositional phrases and postpositional phrases are analysed into two components: a head, which may be phonetically null/empty, and a nominal complement, which is obligatory. This implies that linguistic typology is not usually unequivocal.

Keywords: Feature checking, Genitive constructions, Location nouns, Prepositions/postpositions, Zarma language

Biographical notes: Dr Waheed Ayisa Jayeola is a Senior Lecturer in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU), Ile-Ife, Nigeria. His areas of interest are morphology, syntax, semantics, and language acquisition. He has done extensive work on the syntax of Zarma, a language of the Nilo-Saharan family.

1. Introduction

The aim of this paper is to provide an analysis of the presence of two different adposition classes in Zarma, namely prepositions and postpositions. Similar to what Heath (1998:135-140) reports for Koyra Chiini, a member of the Songhay languages, Zarma has a very few items that are clearly identified as prepositions, though they can serve other functions like coordination and subordination, similar to what Muysken (1987) reported for Saramaccan, and Newman (2000) for Hausa, among others. Besides, Zarma utilises nouns in order to express location, as is the case with many African languages (Ameka, 2003; Aboh, 2005, 2010; Creissels et al., 2008; Nchare & Terzi, 2014).

Zarma superficially has both SVO and SOV word order patterns and equally spots both prepositions and postpositions. This feature poses a daunting challenge to the claim that languages have one adposition class which is either prepositional or postpositional (Ameka 2003:45). This phenomenon indicates that a number of implicational universals proposed by Greenberg (1963) are mere tendencies. Interestingly, Ameka (2003) alludes to the mixing of types (adpositions) within one and the same language. Saramaccan, Muysken (1987), Dutch, Koopman (2000), Ewe (Gbe), Ameka (2003), Kwa, Aboh (2005), and Mandarin Chinese, Djamouri et al. (2013) are among the languages with both prepositions and postpositions. While most linguists agree that postpositions largely derive from nouns, as Abdoulaye (2018: 2) asserts for Zarma, there has not been any scholarly attempt to distinguish location nouns from postpositions in Zarma. Also, the nature and peculiarities of the two distinct adposition classes identified in Zarma have not received any descriptive/theoretical accounts.

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In view of the foregoing, I will argue that one of the few prepositions identified in Zarma has some amount of relationships with verbs, but its behaviour does not show sufficient evidence to make this study agree that prepositions in the language derive from verbs. And, on the basis of their syntactic distributions, I propose that two categories of postpositions are deployed in the language: basic and derived. Similarly, I argue, following Aboh (2005), that derived postpositions obtain from possessive constructions and develop into a functional element. However, certain functional heads may precede or follow their complements, implying surface mixed structures in Zarma. Therefore, following Kayne's (1994) Antisymmetry approach and Biberauer and Sheehan's (2013) notion of 'harmony', I assume that Zarma is of the type Spec-Head-Complement, where the basic building block for phrases and clauses is also fixed.

2. Literature review

There is a plethora of works on the Zarma language (Tersis, 1980; Grigson, 2002; Sibomana, 2008; Abdoulaye & Buba, 2015; Jayeola, 2019, 2020, 2025), among others. The majority of these works focus on different aspects of Zarma syntax, ranging from relative clause constructions to determiner phrases as well as double object constructions and serial verb constructions. Of specific relevance to this study is Abdoulaye (2018), which focuses on the uses of the markers for static location, source, and destination of motion in two West-African languages, Hausa (Chadic) and Zarma (Songhay). As relevant as the focus of Abdoulaye's (2018) work is to the present study, it says nothing about the two distinct adposition classes in Zarma. According to Abdoulaye (2018), the expression of static location and those of source and destination of motion in Zarma are achieved solely by means of postpositions. In fact, no reference is made to the few prepositions available to the language, may be they are not relevant to the subject matter of the study or the author intentionally decides to ignore them.

Though Ruhlen (1976, 1987) and Morseley et al. (1994) do not work on the core aspect of the syntax of Zarma, they make predictions and postulations about the revealing and intriguing disharmony within the building blocks of its phrases and clauses. What is underlying their descriptions of Zarma is that it is non-configurational, for example. There is no canonical order of items within the phrasal and the clausal architecture of the language. This feature, as it is with Zarma, is different from what is found in other Songhay languages, where there is the dominant sentence order (Heath, 1998; Kossmann, 2009; Christiansen, 2010). Undoubtedly, this phenomenon is intriguing, at least within the generativist tradition, and there is no known study that has addressed this feature in Zarma. Accordingly, this paper will examine the properties of the two classes of adposition and go ahead to account for the observed inconsistency or the ordering disharmony in the language with a view to capturing the intuition of the native speakers.

3. Research methodology

The data used for this study were sourced primarily from native speakers by means of interviews with structured sentences formed specifically to show the syntactic behaviour of prepositions versus postpositions and the ensuing asymmetry or disharmony in Zarma word order. Six competent native speakers of Zarma, who speak the variety of the language spoken in Niamey, the capital of the Niger Republic, were consulted; they comprised three males and three females. The bilingual approach to data collection was used to get relevant speech samples recorded and later transcribed for data elucidation through the frame technique. The language consultants were asked to provide the equivalents of the purposively formed sentences in Zarma. Other data relevant to this study were collected from published works, such as linguistic articles and written texts for Zarma speakers and learners. The transcribed data were subjected to interlinear glossing, and the logical meaning or the English translation follows the interlinear gloss.

The lack of proper analytical accounts of the pattern of disharmony found in Zarma in extant works or studies is the main reason for adopting the minimalist program (MP henceforth) proposed in Chomsky (1993, 1995, 2000). The MP is complemented with the Antisymmetry Hypothesis proposed by Kayne (Kayne, 1994). MP, unlike the Principles and Parameters Theory, uses a smaller number of assumptions to capture the syntax of natural language. The major operation used in MP to build syntactic structures is merge, a mathematical operation that combines selected lexical items from the set in a numeration, subject to the binary principle. The LCA (Linear Correspondence Axiom), which is a product of the Antisymmetry Theory, is relevant to this study in the sense that the operation merge generates unordered structures, while the LCA gets the structures ordered.

4. Findings and discussions

4.1. Zarma word order patterns

As contained in the introduction, there is seeming arbitrary order of items even within the projection of the determiner phrase (DP) in Zarma. Consider the following examples in (1 & 2):

- 1a. *kùsò beeri*
pot-Def big
'The big pot'
- 1b. *sana a keyna*
needle Def small
'The small needle'
- 1c. *tàsà beeri fò*
plate big one
'one big plate'

In (1a), the definite marker *ó* is base-merged with the bare noun, *kùsú* ‘pot’, which causes its pronunciation to be affected and a noun modifier *bèèrì*, an adjective meaning ‘big’ follows. (1b) shows that definiteness externally merges with the noun to project into a DP. In (1c) however, a subset of the definite determiner, numeral *fó*, meaning ‘one’, is preceded by the nominal modifier. Also, within the same DP structure, it is possible for the demonstrative, a class of determiners, to precede or follow its complement.

- 2a. *wóí fèjí híbí*
 this sheep black
 ‘This black sheep’
 b. *hánsì beerì híbí ódì*
 dog big black that
 ‘That big black dog’

From examples (1&2), the definite marker follows its complement, whereas the demonstrative may follow or precede its complement, depending on the specific item. The patterns and configurations of this set of data raise questions about the underlying structure or the canonical order of elements in Zarma (Jayeola, 2019). Within its clause, Zarma attests a mixed order; both OV and VO are permissible, at least superficially. It seems like no order is more constrained than the other. This is illustrated with the examples in (3).

- 3a. *áí nà wí fèjí*
 1sg Perf-Pos kill sheep-Indef
 ‘I (have) killed (some) sheep’
 b. *áí nà fèjò wí*
 1sg Perf-Pos sheep-Def kill
 ‘I (have) killed the sheep’

It appears from the meanings assigned to the examples in (3) that a pre-verbal object position is marked for emphasis (Jayeola, 2020, 2025). The same abstraction extends to the two adposition classes in the language, as shown in (4).

- 4a. *A ka fuwo ra*
 3sg come house-Def P
 ‘S/he came into the room’
 b. *A koy fu zá bìi*
 3sg go house-Indef P yesterday
 ‘S/he has gone home since yesterday’
 c. *Ai mana hari haŋ zá susubay*
 1sg Perf-Neg water drink P morning
 ‘I have not drunk water since morning’

Apart from the clear presence of prepositions and postpositions, there is an intriguing form of disharmony common with the Zarma expressions in (4). In (4c), for instance, the preposition *zá* glossed as ‘since’ occurs with a head-final VP that is headed by *haŋ* ‘drink’, and the postposition *rá* translated as ‘in’ occurs with a head-initial VP, as example (5a) indicates. What these examples say about Zarma is contrary to the assumption of functional typological linguists, whose major concern is to see correlations between head and complement uniformities in a language (Ameka, 2003:43). In fact, I do not consider the correlations between the object verb order and postposition in (5b) as a mark of syntactic uniformity, it is rather pragmatically induced. But from a theoretical point of view, I take all the examples in (5) as those in which the θ -marking of arguments of postpositions and case checking are configurationally carried out.

- 5a. *Ramatu dí Halima hábú ó rá*
 Ramatu see Halima market Def P
 ‘Ramatu saw Halima in the market’
 b. *Quadri ná nòòrú sámba Juwerah sè*
 Quadri Perf.Pos money send Juwerah P
 ‘Quadri has sent the money to Juwerah’
 c. *Fati kaŋ guso rá*
 Fati fall hole P
 ‘Fati fell into a hole’

As puzzling as the patterns of the word order in Zarma may appear, it is not an isolated case. According to Djamouri et al. (2013: 74-5), mixed or disharmonic cross-categorial word order properties are permitted by Universal Grammar (UG) and, in light of this assertion, this work sets out to examine the lexical and syntactic properties of prepositions and postpositions in Zarma.

4.2. The class of adposition in Zarma

According to Matthews (2007: 10), the sense of adposition is a cover term for prepositions and postpositions. Regardless of how they are described, prepositions and postpositions belong to the same syntactic category P. Thus, by definition, they are syntactic categories that relate the position of a nominal group to another unit in a sentence. The relationship in this regard may be connected with time, place, or space of the event and a lot more. Based on typological and extended comparative studies, the internal structure of the P projection varies from one language to another, and, as such, in Zarma,

one class of Ps occurs before, and the other class comes after the complement. Each of the two classes of items is discussed in turns, starting with prepositions.

4.3. Zarma prepositions

Let me start by stating that I do not intend to present a comprehensive list of prepositions in the language but to emphasise that the core of the prepositional class in Zarma is formed by the morphemes *ndà*, whose short form is *dà*, translatable as ‘with’, and *zá*, glossed as ‘since’ or ‘from’. The use of these two words as prepositions that precede their DP complements is shown in (6) and (7) respectively:

- 6a. *ái gá á kar ndà gòbù*
 1sg Fut 3sg hit P cane
 ‘I will beat/hit him/her with cane.’
- b. *Abou koy habu ndà Ali*
 Abou go market P Ali
 ‘Abou went to market with Ali’
- 7a. *a koy fu zá bii*
 3sg go house P yesterday
 ‘S/he has gone home since yesterday’
- b. *Usmani à gá sóbéi [PRO]_i néré jí cirey zá súbà*
 Usman Agr Fut begin sell oil red P tomorrow
 ‘Usman will begin to sell palm oil from tomorrow’

In (6), *ndà* performs two different functions; it serves as an instrumental marker in (6a) while it functions as a comitative marker in (6b). On its part, *zá*, as a preposition, indicates the intervening period between the time mentioned and the time under consideration, which may be interpreted as ‘since’ or ‘from’. This is illustrated with the examples in (7). There is one other item that functions as a preposition, whose interpretation is similar to that of *zá* in (7a, b) above. The item is *kala* ‘until’; its use as such is illustrated in (7c).

- 7c. *ai ga goyo kala almari*
 1sg Fut work P evening
 ‘I will work until evening’

From the data in (6 and 7), the nominal complement, for instance. DP is a must in the projection of the PrepPs, pointing to Ps as functional elements with the capacity to assign case to their complements. Apart from their use as core prepositions, there is evidence that this class of items can introduce clauses. This fact raises the question as to how they should be analysed; either as prepositions that take clausal complements or as subordinators that introduce conditional clauses. Consider these examples:

- 8a. *ndà Kadi du nooru boobo, nga ga koy Maradi*
 Sub Kadi get money plenty 3sg Fut go Maradi
 ‘If Kadi obtained/got a huge amount of money, she will go to Maradi’
- b. *ai mana di Kadi za a kaa*
 1sg Perf-Neg see Kadi Sub 3sg come
 ‘I have not seen Kadi since she came/arrived’
- c. *a si kaa kala ai mu koy*
 3sg Fut.Neg come Sub 1sg ? go
 ‘S/he will not come until/till I leave’

Configurationaly, *ndà*, *za*, and *kala* in the examples in (8) are not prepositions that take clauses as their complements; they syntactically occur before subject DPs which originate internally from the Spec-VP of their respective clauses, in line with the unified theta assignment hypothesis (UTAH), Baker (1988), but need to move to the Spec-TP for case checking purposes. Thus, they are without the property of prepositions that *c*-select clause complements in (8). Instead, they are subordinators that introduce dependent clauses and, by implication, I see them as tolerating some amount of ambiguity. Incidentally, tone does not play much of a lexical role in Zarma (Jayeola, 2016).

At the moment, it is not clear whether each of *zá* and *kala* can be used as a coordinator, whereas *ndà* can function as a coordination marker. In (9a), for instance, I assume that *dà*, its short form, is not a preposition because the structure does not have a comitative reading and its syntactic reading does not favour its analysis as a preposition. Structurally, the sentence has a plural subject where two separate individuals jointly carried out the action expressed by the verb. In (9b), the same item is used to conjoin two pronouns that stand in the direct object position of a transitive verb. In (9a, b), *dà* means ‘and’ but based on the context of use, it is interpreted as ‘or’ in (c).

- 9a. *Kadi dà Ramatu ga zuru*
 Kadi Conj Ramatu Fut run
 ‘Kadi and Ramatu will run’
- b. *Usman dí ní dà áí*
 Usman see 2sg Conj 1sg
 ‘Usman saw you and me’

- c. *wofo arañ ga ba, haw ndà feji*
 which 2pl be like cow Conj sheep
 ‘Which do you prefer, a cow or sheep?’

So far, it is obvious that *ndà* is ambiguous between its usage as a preposition, a subordinator, or a coordinator. Its ambiguous categorial status is also evident in its function as a lexical verb, meaning ‘to have’ in (10). Based on morphological compositions and relevant semantic interpretations, the verb ‘to have’ has two forms: positive and negative, (10a) and (10b) respectively. I take the prefixing particle *si* as the item responsible for the negative interpretation of the verb in (10a), while the morpheme *go* serves as its positive counterpart in (10b).

- 10a. *ai sindà moota*
 1sg Neg-have car
 ‘I don’t have a car’
 b. *a gondà fu*
 3sg Pos-have house
 ‘S/he has a house’

Still on its association with verbs, Abdoulaye and Buba (2015:47) report that *ndà* can combine with motion verbs that are naturally intransitive to express a causal meaning. In this case, the causative form of the verb now has a direct relationship with two arguments. This is shown in the examples below, culled from Abdoulaye and Buba *ibid.*

- 11a *Hiimù koy ndà zànk-ey isà mè*
 Himu go CAUS child-Def.Pl river shore
 ‘Himu took the children to the river.’
 b. *Ko-ndà ni beer-òò!*
 go-CAUS 2sg elder-Def
 ‘Take your elder brother!’

Based on the ambiguous status of *ndà*, particularly its close relationships to verbs, there is a tendency that *ndà* has grammaticalized from a verb to a class of prepositions, similar to the distributive identity between verbs and some elements in Kwa and Ewe (Gbe) Aboh (2005:628-9) and Ameka (2003:51) respectively. But, to easily admit that the prepositions identified in Zarma evolve from verbs will be without much argumentation and empiricism because only three items have been identified as prepositions, and only one of them has an identical verbal counterpart. Thus, there is no *prima facie* case for this proposal to hold in the case of Zarma. On the other hand, Aboh and Ameka assume that the development of verbs to prepositions is mediated by serial verb constructions (SVC). Unfortunately, I have not found any clear examples of this instance in Zarma. And, perhaps I should restate here that in the structural realisations of SVC, there exists cross-linguistic variability. For instance, in Ewe SVCs, verbs should share the same aspectual value (Ameka, 2001); this is contrary to the feature found with SVCs in Zarma, where a functional projection, marked with the particle *gà*, separates the two predicates (Jayeola, 2021). Though the behaviour of the functional item is imitative of the Tense/Aspect category, it clearly does not share the same tense/aspect value with the verbs in the series. In fact, Abdoulaye (2018: 63) describes Zarma as a non-serializing language, contrary to Jayeola (Jayeola, 2021). In all, the information about the behaviour of *ndà*, *zá*, and *kala*, having multiple uses, is not unusual or abnormal. The phenomenon has parallels in other languages (Muysken, 1987).

4.4. Zarma Postpositions

Two types or categories of postposition are found in Zarma: the basic and the ones derived from location nouns. I assume that the diachronic sources of the basic ones are not quite transparent, and if at all, they are derived from nouns; these nouns are not known. Interestingly, only two items in the class of basic postpositions have been identified in the synchronic syntax of Zarma.

- 12a. *Fati dé sààrà Mariama sè*
 Fati buy cloth Mariama P
 ‘Fati bought a/the cloth for Mariama’
 b. *Quadri ná nòorú samba Juwerah sè*
 Quadri Perf money send Juwerah P
 ‘Quadri has sent some amount of money to Juwerah’
 13a. *Hama dí Halima hábú ó rá*
 Hama see Halima market Def P
 ‘Hama saw Halima in the market’
 b. *Fati kañ guso rá*
 Fati fall hole P
 ‘Fati fell into a hole’

As example sentences in (12&13) indicate, postpositions virtually share the same feature with prepositions, for instance. They subcategorise for DP complements that precede them. In (12), the particle *sè* is assigned two different interpretations for’ or ‘to’, depending on the semantic relationship the verb has with the entire postpositional phrase. The use of *sè*, particularly in (12b), is in line with its description as a normal postposition for indirect objects (Heath, 1998: 104). However, it may be considered a potential adjunct in (12a), where it serves as the head of the phrase to introduce the

semantic role of beneficiary or recipient, which is not required for the construction to converge. Similarly, *rá* functions as a postposition in (13) to denote ‘in’ for example, location inside as in (13a), or involve a motion sense ‘into’, as indicated by (13b). The locative function of *rá*, as indicated in (13), is similar to other locative postpositions that are usually derived historically from nouns. I shall discuss this below. However, unlike the derived postpositions, there is no specific noun source for *rá* (Heath, 1998:105). If examples under (6) are placed beside those of (12&13), it is not possible to characterise the nominal complements of **Ps** (prepositions and postpositions) in terms of whether they are animate or inanimate. The situation in Zarma is different from what Koopman (2000) reports for Dutch, where DP objects follow prepositions, and inanimate pronominal objects precede.

As I earlier pointed out, some items that are unnatural adpositions because they have noun sources are found in Zarma. This claim finds direct support in Creissels et al. (2008:124), as captured in the following expressions:

“... in the Nilo-Saharan phylum, where adpositions derived from nouns frequently specify the search domain for an object (‘on top of,’ underneath), whereas non-derived adpositions tend to introduce other types of adjuncts, for example, phrases introducing semantic roles such as instrument, beneficiary, or recipient.”

On the basis of the semantic roles of instrument and recipient, which *ndà* and *se* express in (6) and (12) respectively, the two items could be described as non-derived adpositions, following Creissels et al’s prediction. While this description is adequate for *se*, it falls flat for *ndà*, which has been analysed as a derivable functional item, though not from nouns as the above quotation delimits. The implication of this is that the semantic roles of adpositions, as *ndà* and *se* have revealed, might not have anything to do with the origin or source of the adpositions.

The nature of the configurations found in Zarma makes the suspicion rife, that the language employs some items that are not usual or natural adpositions to establish a relationship between one unit of syntactic construct and another. This follows accurately from the above quotation, because adpositions with noun origins in Zarma do specify the search domain for an object, as examples (14-16) illustrate. In spite of their different origins, there is no observable, as well as basic syntactic difference between the basic postpositions (12, 13), and those deemed to have been derived (14-16) below.

- 14a. *ai ga ni donton Muusa doo*
 1sg Fut 2sg send Musa P
 ‘I will send you to Musa’
- b. *ai koy cewo doo bii*
 1sg go book place yesterday
 ‘I went to school yesterday’

In (14a), *doo* functions as a locative postposition and takes the DP *Muusa*, as its complement. In (14b) however, it means ‘at the place of’; the output of which is the combination of the words *cewo* ‘book’ and *doo* ‘place’ to derive the word ‘school’. This may be understood as a form of compounds or what has been described in the literature as a noun-noun construction. Syntactically, the structure in (14b) indicates that *doo*, functioning as a postposition in (14a), derives historically from a noun and has been grammaticalized into a class of postpositions. This is not the only word that fits squarely into this type of characterisation; there are several others, which I shall examine in turn. Let me begin with the postposition *ga*, said to have derived from the word meaning ‘body’, realised as *gaa* in Koyra Chiini and *gahamo* in Zarma.

- 15a. *ai di Abou fondàa ga*
 1sg see Abou path-Def P
 ‘I saw Abou in the street/on the path’
- b. *curey zumbu ai boŋo ga*
 birds-Def descend 1sg head-Def P
 ‘The birds landed on my head’

According to Heath (1998:106), the core sense of *ga* in Koyra Chiini, a language closely related to Zarma, is ‘on’, though it can take on other meanings depending on the verb with which it associates or co-occurs. Other forms of postpositions in Zarma that are derived specifically from nouns, and fit appropriately into Creissels et al’s description, are given in (16) below.

- 16a. *mootaa go gáràjì ó jèrgá*
 car-Def be garage Def P
 ‘The motor car is beside the garage’
- b. *jinay go daaro círé*
 baggage be bed-Def P
 ‘The baggage is under the bed’
- c. *ai koy isa banda*
 1sg go river P
 ‘I went to the back/other side of the river’
- d. *kùsu go taabulo bòŋ*
 pot be table-Def P
 ‘A pot is on the table’
- e. *bòŋ béenú*
 head P
 ‘on the head’

All the items in bold in the examples under (16) are by their syntactic configurations, postpositions that *c-select* DP complements. This view is in line with Heath (1998:107), who describes such items as concrete spatial postpositions that denote space and location. In another vein, they seem, by their syntactic arrangements, to function in (17) as nouns. This is assumed because each of them has its corresponding gloss as a noun in the following words: *jèrgá* ‘side, part of’, *círè* ‘underside’, *banda* ‘back’, *bòŋ* ‘head’ and *bééná* ‘top, sky, upper floor’. Consider the words along the patterns formed in the examples in (17):

- 17a. *beena* *hari*
sky water
‘rain’
- b. *curo* *koy* ***bééná***
bird-Def go high/sky
‘The bird flew up’
- c. ***bòŋo*** *ga* *beeri*
head-Def be big
‘The head is big’
- d. *ai* *hau* *mosoro* ***bòŋo*** *ra*
1sg tie headgear head-Def P
‘I put on headgear’

Based on their syntactic positions as well as the resultant interpretations of the structures in (17), the items in bold are undeniably nouns. In (17a), an instance of a noun-noun construction is activated; two old words (nouns in this case), *beena* ‘sky’ and *hari* ‘water’ which literally translate as ‘sky water’ combine to produce a new word meaning ‘rain’. The status of *beena* ‘high/sky’ in (17b) is not as clear as anyone will assume due to the class of verb it comes after. The verb *koy* ‘go’ can be used both transitively and intransitively, so, if on the one hand it is transitive, it assigns an accusative case that is checked in a complement-head relation to *beena*. If otherwise, I assume that there is a covert P head in the vicinity of *beena*, which makes its appearance in that position legitimate, otherwise, the structure or the derivation crashes. Also, *bòŋo* ‘the head’ functions as the DP subject in (17c), where it checks its nominative case in the Spec-TP position, but serves as the DP complement of the postposition *ra* in (17d). Generally speaking, the fact of (17) is different from what the structures in (18) illustrate.

- 18a. *Fati* *go* *ái* ***jèrgá***
Fati be 1sg beside
‘Fati is beside me’
- b. *ái* ***banda*** *a* *go* *dooru*
1sg back Agr be pain
‘My back is paining /my back aches’
- c. *túró* ***círè*** *à* *gà* *yéyí*
tree-Def underneath Agr be cold
‘The underside of the tree is cold’
- d. *ái* *de* *gòròŋa* ***bòŋ***
1sg buy hen head
‘I bought a hen’s head/head of a hen’

On the basis of syntactic alignments and semantic interpretations of the examples in (18), the bold items unambiguously stand in a possessor-possessed relationship with the items that immediately precede them. For instance, example (18a) can be variably rendered as ‘Fati is by my side’; where *ái*, interpreted as ‘my’ stands in possessor relation to the possessed noun *jèrgá* ‘side’, and the whole DP is assigned an accusative case by default. The same reasoning can be extended to example (18b), where the subject DP, *ái banda* ‘my back’ checks its nominative case in the Spec-TP position. In (18c, d), I observe that the items in bold, which can be described as spatial/locative nouns in those examples, stand in a possessed relation to the nouns that precede them; they are not recognizable as P heads. For instance, the verb *de* ‘buy’ in (18d) is a complement-taking verb, and the DP, *gòròŋa bòŋ* ‘head of a hen’, corresponds to its internal argument that is assigned accusative case.

Under examples (18a, b), there is an instance of pronominal possessive, while (18c, d) are representative examples of DP possessives, where the possessor and the possessed are lexical nouns, and the possessor linearly and rigidly precedes the possessed without any overt item intervening between them. In view of its structural relationship and relevance to the analysis of derived postpositions in Zarma, I think a very short discussion of the DP-possessive type is desirable here, because the situation in Zarma is different from languages like Nweh, Nkemnji (1995), Tadaksahak, Christiansen (2010), where a specific marker is designated as the linker of the two DPs. In the case of Zarma, the formation of this type of genitive is simply by pre-head adjunction, which is without any special linking devices of a segmental or a tonal nature (Kossmann, 2009:2). Consider the following examples in (19) alongside the ones in (18).

- 19a. *Fati* *fâfâ*
fati breast
‘Fati’s breast/breast of Hama’
- b. *Baro* *kùàrà*
Baro house

- c. 'Baro's house/house of Baro'
bónkònó hisó
 king-Def daughter
 'The king's daughter/ the daughter of the king'

In each of the examples in (18c, d) and (19), we have two nominal elements that stand in an equidistance relationship to each other, whose collective interpretations predict that *something* unknown connects them. In this regard, therefore, I aver that, of the two categories of genitive identified in the literature: free or 'of' genitive and construct or S-genitive, Zarma attests the construct or S-genitive type, in conformity with the structure proposed by Abney (1987). According to him, the genitive phrase is projected by a functional D head filled by the Saxon's found in English, which is captured in the examples below.

- 20a. Mary's sister
 b. The president's lodge
- Given the characteristics of the noun-noun genitive, predictable from the examples in (18, 19), I propose that the genitive marker is a covert element that does not have PF representation but can be interpreted appropriately at the LF. And, on the strength of this proposal, I present the projection of the DP-possessive expression in Zarma in (21), using the object DP in example (18d).

The assumption that the head of the DP in Zarma possessive determiner is null, derives from the evidence that the unpronounced determiner has specific semantic properties (for example, a marker of possession), based on the glosses/interpretations provided for the data in (18c-d & 19). This follows from a core assumption within the MP that all heads and maximal projections must be interpretable at the semantic interface; incidentally, the proposed null determiner analysed in (21) undoubtedly contributes to the meaning of the expression(s) (Chomsky, 1995). Therefore, I roughly speculate that the null-D contains an abstract affix or free-standing morpheme that carries an interpretable D-feature. On the strength of the foregoing, I wish to tentatively aver, following Aboh (2005, 2010), that the class of items recognised as concrete spatial nouns by Heath (1998) has developed into a functional head, postposition, by means of possessive constructions. Although, the structure in Zarma is quite different from Ewe (Gbe), where body part nouns differ from the derived postpositions in the way they are linked to their possessors (Ameka, 2003:59). The development of this class of nouns into postpositions, as the data in (22) below will reveal, automatically leads to the elimination of the null-D assumption, because the output of the structure no longer has semantic properties of possession. It, however, has direct influence on the surface order of the P heads and their complements.

The grammatical relations between these items and other units within the clause where they occur provide evidence for them to be described and recognised as postpositions. Consider the data in (22):

- 22a. *Zainabou go daáró bòŋ*
 Zainabou be bed-Def P
 'Zainabou is on the bed'
- b. *Zainabou dàŋ bònkàrè táabùlò bòŋ*
 Zainabou put cloth table-Def P
 'Zainabou put a cloth on the table'

Contrary to what (21) indicates, *bòŋ*, in (22a), is a P that selects *daáró* 'bed' as its complement, while the entire PP functions as the complement of the subject DP. The functional item *bòŋ*, a P, expresses the location of the event denoted by the verb *dàŋ* 'put', a three-place argument verb in (22b). If *bòŋ* is deleted from (22a), then the derivation will definitely not converge, but its absence in (22b) does not affect its grammaticality as indicated by the convergence of (23). The correctness of (23) speaks volumes about Aboh's (2005) recognition of the deletion hypothesis as a universal feature of adpositions.

23. *Mariama dàŋ bònkàrè táabùlò*
 Mariama put cloth table-Def
 'Mariama put a/the cloth on the table'

Given the fact that *dàŋ* 'put' corresponds to the class of verbs that takes one nominal and one prepositional or postpositional complement, I consider *táabùlò* 'the table' in (23) as the DP complement of a PP whose head P is phonetically null/empty. I take this position because *bònkàrè* 'cloth', the direct object of put, and *táabùlò* 'the table' together do not form or constitute a grammatical whole.

The null-P assumption does not seem to discriminate between the two classes of postposition: basic and derived. Similar to (23), for the P category that I describe as basic, the deletion hypothesis still applies, though this may depend largely on the organisation of the sentence. Let us put the grammaticality of (24b) into perspective.

- 24a. *áí dí Kadi hábú ó rá*
 1sg see Kadi market Def P
 'I saw Kadi inside the market'

- b. *ái dí Kadi hábú*
 1sg see Kadi market
 ‘I saw Kadi in the market’

In (24b), the postposition *rá* is deemed to be deleted or non-overt. If this is not so, it will be impossible to specify the unit that assigns case to *hábu*, since *dí* ‘see’ is a mono-argument verb that has a case feature already checked by *Kadi*, its only internal argument.

Similar to my explanation above, the null adposition account is relevant to the requirements that the stranded DP complement must receive case and be appropriately theta-marked by the head P. Consider the following examples in (25):

- 25a. *Kimba ná bónkàrè dàṅ táabùlò bòn*
 Kimba Perf cloth put table-Def P
 ‘Kimba has put THE CLOTH on the table’
 b. *Kimba dàṅ bónkàrè táabùlò (bòn)*
 Kimba put cloth table-Def (P)
 ‘Kimba put the cloth on the table’
 c. **Kimba dàṅ bónkàrè*
 Kimba put cloth

The natural character of the ditransitive verb *dàṅ* ‘put’ which is of the subcategory V [DP __ DP PP] makes the prediction of a null P head in (25) a viable option. Here, the third argument of the verb for example, the PP seems to function like a complement; its absence renders the resulting construction ungrammatical as example (25c) shows. Example (25a) converges because the P head, *bòn* ‘on’, assigns case to its complement *táabùlò* while the direct object *bónkàrè* ‘cloth’ occurs at the specifier position of the verb *dàṅ* ‘put’ where its emphatic feature is licensed. (25b) is a neutral sentence in which the direct object of the verb, *bónkàrè* ‘cloth’, checks its accusative case in a head-complement relation and the DP, *táabùlò* ‘the table’, which serves as the complement of the unfilled P head cannot freely move away from its head because it is required to satisfy the P feature of space. This is one of the properties of derived or locative postpositions in Zarma, which I shall discuss in the section that follows. Thus, in (25b), the empty P category governs, and case marks its complement in compliance with the Minimal Link Condition or adjacency condition. This is not the same with what is found in Ewe (Gbe) where postpositions do not have case-assigning functions (Ameka, 2003:61-2).

4.5. Properties of prepositions and postpositions in Zarma

There are semantic and syntactic criteria that can be used to differentiate the two categories or classes of P in Zarma. From the earlier discussions of prepositions and postpositions, I assume that postpositions generally encode location while prepositions largely include path designators, but they both belong to a closed class. Structurally, it is possible for prepositions in Zarma to move along with their complements, as shown in examples under (26), similar to the situation in Yoruba (Abimbola, 2024:73), but it is not allowable to take their complements away from them as indicated in (27). As the grammaticality of the sentences in (27) would lead us to believe, *zá* and *ndà*, both serving as prepositions, can be dropped, covert or null.

- 26a. [*zá súbà*]_i à gá sintí gà néré jí cirey t_i
 P tomorrow 3sg Fut begin FP sell oil red
 ‘As from tomorrow, she/he will start/begin to sell palm oil’
 b. [*ndà gòbù*]_i nò áí gá á kar t_i
 P cane Foc 1sg Fut 3sg hit
 ‘I will beat/hit him/her WITH CANE’
 27a [*súbà*]_i à gá sintí gà néré jí cirey t_i
 tomorrow 3sg Fut begin FP sell oil red
 ‘As from tomorrow, she/he will start/begin to sell palm oil’
 b. [*gòbù*]_i nò áí gá á kar t_i
 cane Foc 1sg Fut 3sg hit
 ‘I will beat/hit him/her WITH CANE’
 28a. **[súbà]*_i à gá sintí gà néré jí cirey zá t_i
 tomorrow 3sg Fut begin FP sell oil red P
 b. **[gòbù]*_i nò áí gá á kar ndà t_i
 cane Foc 1sg Fut 3sg beat P

Example (28a) is ungrammatical because *zá* cannot remain in situ while its complement is moved in a topic construction, and (28b) crashes because the focused DP, *gòbù* ‘cane’ cannot front, stranding *ndà* in the source position. In sum, prepositions, as revealed by the data, do not license a following gap.

As opposed to what prepositions present, one of the basic postpositions, the dative *sè*, may strand or pied-pipe with the preceding DP, and no resumptive pronoun is required. When the indirect object of the dative *sè* is a content question item or what is popularly referred to as a wh-item, for the derivation to converge, the whole postpositional phrase can undergo movement, where the postposition *sè* ‘for’, illustrated with (29a), can be dragged along with its complement *mái* ‘who’. It is also possible to propose just the content question item, leaving out the head of the dative postposition to

strand, which explains why example (29b) is well-formed. Example (29c) is non-convergent because it is not possible to drop or have a covert realisation of the dative *sè*.

- 29a. [máí sè]_i nò ní dè sààrà t_i
 who P Foc 2sg buy cloth
 ‘Whom did you buy the cloth for?’
 b. [máí]_i nò ní dè sààrà t_i sè
 who Foc 2sg buy cloth P
 ‘Whom did you buy the cloth for?’
 c. *[máí]_i nò ní dè sààrà t_i
 who Foc 2sg buy cloth

It is, however, puzzling to observe that the other basic postposition *rá*, only allows its complement DP to move along with it, for example. pied-piping; it does not permit stranding. Accordingly, in the focused constructions in (30a), *rá* must move alongside its complement. It is ungrammatical to strand the postposition as in (30b), but it is permissible to drop the postposition as example (30c) indicates. This is the same as (24b).

- 30a. [hábo rá]_i nò áí dí Kadi t_i
 market-Def P Foc 1sg see Kadi
 ‘I saw Kadi INSIDE THE MARKET’
 b. *[hábo]_i nò áí dí Kadi t_i rá
 market-Def Foc 1sg see Kadi P
 c. [hábo]_i nò áí dí Kadi t_i
 market-Def Foc 1sg see Kadi
 ‘I saw Kadi INSIDE THE MARKET’

The data in (30) show that *rá* does not manifest the same distributive property as *sè* in (29). This absence of a uniform syntactic characterisation may have something to do with the different origins of the two postpositions, keeping apart their different semantic imports. I assume this to be the case, considering the behaviour of *ga*, a locative postposition assumed to derive, probably, from *gahám* ‘body’ (Heath, 1998). Consider the structure in (31):

- 31a. à koy ce ga
 3sg go leg P
 ‘S/he went on foot’
 b. [ce ga]_i nò à koy t_i
 leg P Foc 3sg go
 ‘S/he went ON FOOT’
 c. [ce]_i nò à koy t_i
 leg Foc 3sg go
 ‘S/he went ON FOOT’
 d. *[ce]_i nò à koy t_i ga
 leg Foc 3sg go

As it is with *rá* in (30), *ga* cannot strand, but it can be covert or dropped. The absolute similarity in the syntactic behaviour of *ga* and *ra* may be sufficient to treat them as allomorphs of a single morpheme. This prediction is supported by the example in (32), where the two items can be used interchangeably without affecting the interpretation of the sentence.

32. ai di Abou fonda ga/ra
 1sg see Abou path-Def P
 ‘I saw Abou in the street/on the path’

Example (32) indicates that either *ga* or *ra* can be used in that context to achieve the same meaning as shown by the interpretation assigned to the sentence. Other derived postpositions, *cirè*, *doò*, *jèrgá*, and *bòn*, which I discussed earlier, share a common distributive property with *ga* and *rá*. This is illustrated in the representative examples in (33):

- 33a. [táabùlò cirè]_i nò Abou dàṅ gùlèsè t_i
 table-Def P Foc Abou put cup
 ‘Abou put the cup UNDER THE TABLE’
 b. [Muusa doo]_i nò ai ga ni donton t_i
 Musa P Foc 1sg Fut 2sg Send
 ‘I will send you TO MUSA’
 c. [gàràjì ó jèrgá]_i nò mootaa gòò t_i
 garage Def P Foc motor-Def be
 ‘The motor is BESIDE THE GARAGE’
 d. [táabùlò bòn]_i nò Zainabou dàṅ bónkàrè t_i
 table-Def P Foc zainabou put cloth
 ‘Zainabou put the cloth ON THE TABLE’

The data in (33) show that the entire postpositional phrase can be focused to appear at the specifier position of a focus phrase, which is headed by *nò*, leaving a phonetically null copy at the extraction site.

- 34a. [táabùlò]_i nò Abou dàṅ gùlésè t_i
 table-Def Foc Abou put cup
 ‘Abou put the cup ON/UNDER THE TABLE’
- b. [Muusa]_i nò ai ga ni donton t_i
 Musa Foc 1sg Fut 2sg send
 ‘I wii send you TO MUSA’
- c. [gàràjì ó]_i nò moota go t_i
 garage Def Foc motor be
 ‘The motor is IN/BESIDE THE GARAGE’
- d. [tábùlò]_i nò Zainabou dàṅ bónkàrè t_i
 table-Def Foc Zainabou put cloth
 ‘Zainabou put the cloth ON/UNDER THE TABLE’

What is found with (34) differs from what (33) depicts. There is the tendency for the postpositions to be phonetically null as observed in (34), but stranding is prohibited as (35) suggests.

- 35a. *[táabùlò]_i nò Abou dàṅ gùlésè t_i círè
 table-Def Foc Abou put cup P
 b. *[Muusa]_i nò Ai ga ni donton t_i doo
 Musa Foc 1sg Fut 2sg Send P
 c. *[gàràjì ó]_i nò moota go t_i jèrgá
 garage Def Foc motor be P
 d. *[tábùlò]_i nò Zainabou dàṅ bónkàrè t_i bònṅ
 table-Def Foc Zainabou put cloth P

Basically, I assume that sentences in (35) are non-convergent simply because stranding is not allowed; the postpositions must either move along with their focused DP complements to the clause initial position viz pied-piping or be deleted/phonetically null. With respect to their syntactic representations, derived postpositions share at least one feature in common with genitive constructions. This idea finds support in (36), where the possessor and the possessed items can be moved via focus to the clause-initial position, and a silent/unpronounced copy of the focused genitive DP is left behind.

- 36a. Kadi dé Garba fu
 Kadi buy Garba house
 ‘Kadi bought Garba’s house’
- b. [Garba fu]_i nò Kadi dé t_i fu
 Garba house Foc Kadi buy
 ‘Kadi bought GARBA’s HOUSE’

In the neutral sentence in (36a), the genitive DP, *Garba fu* ‘Garba’s house’, entirely functions as the complement of the verb *dé* ‘buy’ while it gets raised to Spec-FocP, and a phonetically null copy is left at the extraction site in (36b). I do not consider the shared syntactic identity arbitrary; it may, after all, confirm the claim that derived postpositions are products of possessive constructions, except that different syntactic explanations are required for their derivation. In what follows, however, there is a feature that separates genitive constructions from derived postpositions. For instance, in (36c), it is possible for the possessor alone to be fronted and focus-marked, leaving the possessed item behind at the base-generated position. Under this condition, the movement of the possessor DP by means of focus does not induce the appearance of a resumptive pronoun.

- 36c. [Garba]_i nò Kadi dé t_i fu
 Garba Foc Kadi buy house
 ‘Kadi bought GARBA’s house’

Also, there are a number of differences between locative nouns, which belong to an open class, and the postpositions derived from them, which constitute a closed class. A closer look at the environments where they appear shows that the locative noun is attested in the subject position (37a), while the postposition is ruled out in (37b).

- 37a. bònṅ ga beeri
 head-Def be big
 ‘The head is big’
- b. *bònṅ ga beeri
 on be big

The noun, *bònṅ* ‘the head’ is qualified to serve as the subject of the clause in (37a), whereas its postpositional counterpart, meaning ‘on’, cannot function in this way as (37b) indicates. I assume that (37b) is ungrammatical because the postposition, *bònṅ* ‘on’, cannot occur independent of its complement, whereas its noun counterpart does not need one (37a). Conversely, when the item (*bònṅ*) or any other particle in this category occurs with a purported complement and functions as the subject or object in a clause, it is rather logical to analyse such a configuration as a possessive construction rather than a postpositional phrase. Consider the examples in (38):

- 38a. áí de gónḍi bònṅ
 1sg buy snake head

- 'I bought a snake's head/head of a snake'
- b. *i kaaru fuwo bòŋ*
 3pl climb house-Def head
 'They climbed the house'
- c. *tasa ra a ga ziibi*
 plate inside Agr be dirty
 'The inner part of the plate is dirty'

The contexts in (38a & b) indicate that *bòŋ* refers to the 'head' but not to the spatial location on the head of the snake and the house, respectively. It is rather the case that the phrases *gòndì bòŋ* 'snake's head' and *fuwo bòŋ* 'the top of the house', are possessive constructions where it is not possible to interpret *bòŋ* as 'on'. In (38a, b), *bòŋ* does not license a case; it serves as the complement of a null possessive head, and *gòndì* 'snake' functions in the specifier position of the possessive phrase; therefore, *bòŋ* is not a postposition. Similarly, in the context of example (38c), *ra* does not function as a locative postposition because it does not denote location inside the plate. Instead, the configuration expresses an inherent part of the plate, which is the possessor. Nonetheless, it (*ra*) may be used to denote location inside of its DP complement, only when it functions as the P head that assigns an appropriate case to its complement. This is the case with (39a), whose structural analysis is presented in (39b)

- 39a. *ni di ai na fuwo ra*
 2sg see 1sg mother house-Def P
 'You saw my mother in/inside the house'

The analysis in (39b) indicates that the entire PP, *fuwo ra* 'in/inside the house', headed by *ra*, is an adjunct to the verb *di* 'see'; the absence of the PP does not make the derivation ungrammatical. In this instance, therefore, *ra* has case assigning properties, making the occurrence of *fuwo* 'the house' legitimate in the structure. This fact about Zarma contradicts some proposals in the linguistic literature that postpositions are not adpositions, because they cannot assign case (Ameka, 2003:61). In fact, the structure in (40) crashes because the DP, *fuwo*, is neither a grammatical nor a meaningful unit of the clause; it is not accessible to case and theta.

40. **ni di ai na fuwo*
 2sg see 1sg mother house-Def

One implicit understanding of the inadmissibility of (40) is that the postposition *ra* 'in/inside' is required for the derivation to converge, since its understood DP complement, *fuwo* 'the house', will be deemed to occur in a position where case licensing requirement cannot be met, contra case filter. Besides, possibly due to the nature or peculiarity of the configuration, the null P account cannot apply in (40), contrary to what (24b) presupposes, implying that the null P assumption does not apply indiscriminately, at least in Zarma.

The ill-formed sentence in (40) can be repaired or restructured to take on a different syntax and meaning as the grammatical and acceptable form in (41) illustrates.

- 41a. *ni di ai na fu*
 2sg see 1sg mother house
 'You saw my mother's house'

Based on the interpretation deducible from (41a), the whole composite of *ai na fu* 'my mother's house', analysed as a possessive phrase, will take an accusative case from the verb *di* 'see', in a complement head relation. The structure is analysed in (41b).

In the instance analysed in (41b), *fu*, ‘house’, is an NP that sits in the complement position of a null possessive head, thus, can no longer take on a definite feature as in (39), (see Jayeola 2019 for a discussion of this constraint). Similarly, derived postpositions, unlike their noun counterparts, cannot serve as modifiers of determiners (definite/indefinite). This is confirmed by the grammaticality and otherwise of (42) and (43) respectively.

- 42a. *bòŋo ga beeri*
 head-Def be big
 ‘The head is big’
 b. *beena a ga ziibi*
 sky Def be dark
 ‘The sky is dark’

- 43a. **koy ga daŋ gulese taabulo bòŋo*
 go FP put cup table-Def on-Def
 b. **curo koy bòŋ béená a*
 bird-Def go head on-Def

It is discernible from (42) that locative nouns can be used as common referential nouns, in which case, they are followed by the determiner that may fuse with the noun (42a) or be realised as a free-standing morpheme (42b). This is not possible when the items are used as postpositions, providing the requisite explanation for the ill-formed structures in (43). Similarly, a locative noun may be modified by an adjective as shown in (44), where the adjective *keyna* ‘small’ modifies the noun *bòŋ* ‘head’ but this possibility is not available to its postpositional counterpart. The occurrence of the adjective *keyna* ‘small’ after the postposition *bòŋ* ‘on’ renders example (44b) incomprehensible.

- 44a. *a si nda bòŋ keyna*
 3sg Neg have head small
 ‘S/he does not have a small head’
 b. **koy ga daŋ gulese taabulo bòŋ keyna*
 go FP put cup table-Def P small

In a nutshell, the two basic divisions of the category P are not too different in terms of their distribution and in relation to their syntactic behaviour. It has been shown that these items share similarities and differences to some extent, though there is no overlapping membership in the category. It is obvious from the descriptions of the data that stranding is not an absolute feature that can be used to distinguish prepositions from postpositions in Zarma. In all contexts, the dative postposition *se* cannot be dropped. The arguments presented in this study appear convincing enough to treat prepositions and postpositions as different lexical categories, and the derived postpositions appear to have undergone a process of grammaticalization, which is why they do not show the usual properties of typical genitive constructions, for example, derived postpositions are potential case assigners.

4.6. Antisymmetry and Zarma disharmonic word order

Apart from the fact that prepositions and postpositions are clearly distinguished by their linear position, other convincing evidences abound that limit their distributive and syntactic features as the only indices that can cause prepositions to be distinguished from postpositions. For instance, prepositions and postpositions, except the dative *se*, may be dropped, though not in all cases, as a number of examples have shown. The fact that *se* cannot be dropped is at least a confirmation that postposition is a head that *c-selects* for a DP complement. In what may be compared to the English dative, when the indirect object occurs before the direct object in Zarma, the dative *se* is not dropped, but it gives a different reading to the sentence. This phenomenon is illustrated with the data under (45).

- 45a. *A no ai se haw*
 3sg give 1sg P cow
 ‘S/he gave a cow to ME’
 b. *Iri ga no ni se nooru*
 1pl Fut give 2sg P money
 ‘We will give money to YOU’

This strand of evidence, among others, does not favour or support the assumption by some generativists that only a member of the category P should have a case-assigning function (Ameka, 2003; Aboh, 2005). Furthermore, I do not have data evidence to show where postpositions occur as complements of prepositions in Zarma, and can therefore not make use of the criterion to describe postpositions as lacking case assignment properties in the language.

Having discussed the internal structures of prepositions and postpositions in Zarma, I wish to go on to the discussion of asymmetry between SOV and prepositions on the one hand, and SVO and postpositions on the other. I assume, following the preceding account, that the word order pattern in the Zarma PP is determined by the lexical content of the P^o node, because the head can precede or follow its complement. In other words, I consider the surface order within the PP as a kind of reordering that takes place at the PF level, where the base-generated order is conditionally altered. Consider, in this regard, examples under (4) repeated here as (46) for ease of reference:

- 46a. *A ka fuwo ra*
 3sg come house-Def P
 ‘S/he came into the room’
- b. *A koy fu zá bii*
 1sg go house P yesterday
 ‘S/he has gone home since yesterday’
- c. *Ai mana hari hay za susubay*
 1sg Perf-Neg water drink P morning
 ‘I have not drunk water since morning’

A greater degree of flexibility occurs in (46), where, for instance, in (a), *fuwo ra*, a postposition phrase functions as an adjunct to the verb *ka* ‘come’, which is used intransitively. In (b), on the other hand, another adjunct, this time around, a preposition phrase, occurs with a head first predicate, *koy fu* ‘go home’. The view about conditional alteration is even more pronounced with the disharmony in the grammatical structure in (c), where the verb phrase displays OV order but takes a prepositional phrase adjunct.

Contrary to the conditional alteration perception, the ungrammaticality of the examples in (47) points to one fact, which is that alterations on the base-generated order are not unconstrained. Unconditionally, Zarma systematically disallows prepositions from taking DPs to their left, while postpositions are barred from selecting DPs to their right.

- 47a. **a ka ra fuwo*
 3sg come P house-Def
- b. **ai koy fuu bii za*
 1sg go house yesterday P

The set of sentences in (46) does not regiment word orders in Zarma into dominant and recessive; thus, it is difficult to say with precision when to have harmonic or disharmonic constructions.

According to Jayeola (2020), the OV order in Zarma is derived because the direct object that originates at the complement position of V moves to its specifier position to check its emphatic feature in a spec-head relation. This unitary approach provides a technical generalisation in the direction of harmony in the Zarma word order. The generalisation that can be formulated in this respect is that head-final categories found with DP, VP, and PostP are superficially what they are because their complements move to a higher position for case-driven reasons. This proposal is consistent with Kayne’s universal word order of Spec-Head-Complement order, and that what is described as a head-final or a head-initial category is a language-particular property. For instance, in Chinese, there is a systematic difference between head-initial and head-final categories with respect to how they interact with case (Djamouri et al., 2013: 89).

Under this approach, there is the assumption that the DP complement of the postposition originates at a base position after the P but should move to some spec-position at some point in the derivation. According to Zeijlstra (2013), movement could either be for syntactic or semantic reasons, and once it is syntactic, a constituent is considered to move for the purpose of checking features, in line with the economy principle of *Procrastinate*. Thus, as it is with DPs and VPs, I assume that the P^o head of a PostP in Zarma has a strong EPP feature which triggers its complement to move before *spell-out* so as to ensure that phonetic and semantic features are processed by separate components of the grammar, for example, the PF component and the LF component, respectively. This account, which is strictly in line with the prediction of the Minimalist Program, does not depend solely on the EPP features of P^o; the movement is also meant to satisfy the case checking requirement of the P^o complement, since a derivation crashes when the EPP feature is not present and the case feature on the DP is not checked.

Consequently, I aver that the DP with a dative or oblique case feature enters a checking relation with the P^o that has a matching feature in a spec-head relation. And, as it is the tradition in the minimalist program, applications of operations *merge* and *move* allow any given category to have a number of specifiers; therefore, the P head licenses a specifier and allows its complement to check its Case under a Spec-head relation. This is illustrated in (48).

The structure in (48) nicely accounts for the surface order of constituents within the PP, and in conformity with my proposal for a phonetically null P head in some situations, the configuration in (48) is still in order, except that in such cases, the P° is phonetically null. One more theoretical implication of the analysis pursued in this paper is that both the Head-Movement Constraint and the principle of Least Effort, otherwise understood as Minimal Link Condition, are clearly underscored and satisfied by the analysis in (48).

5. Conclusion

The data used for this study confirm or corroborate the claim for the co-existence of both prepositions and postpositions in some languages. However, the syntactic characteristics of these two classes of adposition in Zarma are somewhat not the same with what is found in some other languages. This is probably due to the breakdown in the traditional word order correlation, which predicts that SVO languages should spot preposition while SOV counterparts should display postposition. The Zarma data analysed in this research show that VO can occur with postposition and OV can equally appear with preposition, each within the same minimal clause. This study establishes that only one of the items identified as postpositions does not have its origin from location nouns; others derive diachronically from nouns but are analysed to have grammaticalised into functional heads, and there is not much evidence to postulate that prepositions are derived from verbs. Relying on their distribution and syntactic properties, this work posits that there are no stark contrasts between prepositions and postpositions; rather, they both instantiate the same basic category, PP. Also, prepositions cannot be distinguished from postpositions on the basis of their interaction with case, as has been proposed in other studies. This study further reveals that the major difference between the two types of PP is related to the direction of case-checking; complements of prepositions check their case in a head-complement relation, while the DP complements of postpositions check their case through movement that is mediated by *procrastinate* in a specifier-head relation.

The implication of the findings of this study is that the nominal origin of the majority of the postpositions does not greatly impact their ability to license case, and the postpositions do not behave the same way as the nouns they are understood to have evolved from. They can also not be employed as common referential nouns, should not be followed by the determiner, cannot be modified by an adjective, and cannot stand alone, but they license case. In line with the universal order proposed by Kayne (1994), the paper concludes that the θ -marking of arguments of PPs and case checking are configurationally carried out. Finally, the approach adopted in this study reveals that traditional or extant linguistic typologies are usually not unequivocal; thus, the different accounts contained in the literature might not easily apply cross-linguistically. Also, future syntactic investigations of languages in the Nilo-Saharan family, especially the ones that are non-configurational, will benefit from the outcome of this study because it might provide helpful insights about how recurring linguistic properties can reveal important language-dependent facts as well as cross-linguistic variations.

ORCID

Waheed Ayisa Jayeola <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6009-3655>

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List of Abbreviations

Agr = Agreement marker, CAUS = Causative, Conj = Conjunction, Def = Definite, DP = Determiner Phrase, EPP = Extended Projection Principle, Foc = Focus marker, FocP = Focus Phrase, FP = Functional Projection, Fut = Future, LCA = Linear Correspondence Axiom, LF = Logical Form, MP = Minimalist Program, Neg = Negative Marker/Negation, N = Noun, P = Preposition/Postposition, Perf = Perfective Aspect, PF = Phonetic Form, Pl = Plural, PP = Preposition/Postposition Phrase, Pos = Positive Sg = Singular, SOV = Subject Object Verb, Spec = Specifier, Sub = Subordinator, SVC = Serial Verb Construction, SVO = Subject Verb Object, TP = Tense Phrase, UG = Universal Grammar, V = Verb, VP = Verb Phrase, * = Denotes an ungrammatical expression, 1 = First Person, 2 = Second Person, 3 = Third Person

